

Sighting of Rufous-Bellied Niltava *Niltava Sundara* (Hodgson, 1837) from Western Ghats: Southern India

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Rufous-bellied Niltava is a resident bird inhabited the bushes and undergrowth nearby water bodies in broad leaved or mixed coniferous forests from Himalayas to Arunachal Pradesh in north east hill states of India (270 to 3200m asl). It shows altitudinal movements and also distributed in north Pakistan (1800-2600m asl), Nepal (800-3200m asl), Bhutan (245-2930m asl) and, in Bangladesh it is a winter vagrant (Grimmett *et al.* 1998 and 2011, Kazmierczak 2000, Ali 2002, Rasmussen and Anderton 2012, Norman 2014, Grewal and Bhatia 2014). Rufous-bellied Niltava is a least concerned (BirdLife 2015, IUCN 2015) bird breeds at 1500-2700m asl during April-July in foothills of Pakistan, Himalayas and northeast states of India.

During our regular field work in Western Ghats, to our surprise on 26.10.2014 at 8.40AM one of author NSV sighted male Rufous-bellied Niltava *Niltava sundara* (Fig. 1) in Amboli forest (15°57'27.95" N 73°59'50.65" E, Fig. 2) in Sawantwadi taluk of Sindadurg district in Southern Maharashtra. The bird was photographed and identified by using field guides by Grimmett *et al.* 1998, Kazmierczak 2000, Rasmussen and Anderton 2012, Norman 2014 and, Grewal and Bhatia 2014. Male Rufous-bellied Niltava is dark blue with underparts orange-rufous colored extending up to vent; undertail coverts is light yellow; forehead, chin, throat is ultramarine blue; crown is pale blue. Since, the Rufous-bellied Niltava is restricted to Himalayas and north east hill states of Indian subcontinent, Pakistan, Nepal, Bhutan and Bangladesh. It is surprising to sight the said bird in Western Ghats of southern India. But, our first photographic evidence confirms Rufous-bellied Niltava existence in the Western Ghats of southern India. Further observations are needed to assess its residential or migratory status in Western Ghats.

Figure 1. Shows Male Rufous-bellied Niltava

Figure 2. Shows sighting place of Rufous-bellied Niltava in Western Ghats

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

References

1. Ali, S. 2002. *The book of Indian birds*, Thirteenth edition. Bombay Natural History Society / Oxford University Press, Mumbai.
2. Bird Life International (2015) Species factsheet: *Niltava sundara*. Downloaded from <http://www.birdlife.org> on 29/10/2015.
3. Grewal, B and Bhatia, G. 2014. *A Naturalist's Guide to the Birds of India, Pakistan, Nepal, Bhutan and Sri Lanka*. Prakash Books India Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi, India.
4. Grimmett, R., Inskipp C. and Inskipp T. 1998. *Birds of the Indian Subcontinent*. Oxford University Press, New Delhi.
5. Grimmett, R., Inskipp, C. and Inskipp, T. 2011. *Birds of the Indian Subcontinent* Second edition. Christopher Helm, Oxford University Press, India.
6. Kazmierczak, K. 2000. *Birds of India, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh and the Maldives* First Edition. Christopher Helm, London.
7. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2015-3. <www.iucnredlist.org>. Downloaded on 29 October 2015.
8. Norman A. 2014. *Birds of India, Pakistan, Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka*, William Collins, An imprint of HarperCollins Publishers, London.
9. Rasmussen P. C. and Anderton J. C. 2012. *Birds of South Asia. The Ripley Guide*. Vol. 1 and 2. Second edition. National Museum of Natural History – Smithsonian Institution, Michigan State University and Lynx Edicions, Washington, DC., Michigan and Barcelona.

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